

Flavonoid Compounds in Licorice Root

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LICORICE (liquorice), the root of various species of *Glycyrrhiza* (Leguminosae) having a sweet taste has long been employed as a flavouring and sweetening agent as well as demulcent and expectorant in western countries, while it has been well known in oriental medicine since ancient times as a very important component of various prescriptions acting as antispasmodic agent, calminative and antidote. Recently, licorice has been recognized as an anti-ulcer and anti-inflammatory agent. In 1946 Revers¹ in Netherlands noted that medicine consisting of licorice extract, anise fruits and reduced iron powder is used for gastric ulcer and licorice extract has been demonstrated to be effective against ulcer by the clinical tests, whereas some side-effects such as edema and hypertension have been observed among the patients treated orally with its higher dose. These side-effects have later been proved as being caused by the mineral corticoid-like action of glycyrrhizin (1), a main saponin constituent of licorice. Kumagai and Yano² have shown that I and its sapogenin, glycyrrhetic acid, inhibit the metabolic reduction of the $\Delta^{4,5}$ -3 keto system in the A-ring and the carbonyl in the side-chain of endogenous cortisol to enhance its activity. Avoiding the side-effects of glycyrrhizin, the non-glycyrrhizin fractions of licorice were investigated by Takagi and his co-workers³ to find that a fraction

tentatively named FM 100 is effective to prevent digestive gastric ulcer by suppressing the gastric secretion. A chemical study showed that the FM-100 fraction of Tongpei Licorice (North-eastern Chinese licorice) contains various flavonoid compounds. The FM-100 fraction is prepared from the methanolic extracts of licorice on treatment with chloroform and benzene followed by shaking with aq. Na₂CO₃ and column chromatography of the acidic fraction. The flavonoid compounds of FM-100 fraction are mostly derived from the outer tissue of licorice root.

Prior to this, it has been known that a flavanone glucoside, liquiritin (2) and its aglycone, liquiritigenin (5)⁴⁻⁸ as well as a corresponding chalcone glucoside, isoliquiritin (6) and its aglycone, isoliquiritigenin (10)⁷⁻¹⁰, are contained in licorice. It has also been shown that isoliquiritin and isoliquiritigenin represent the antispasmodic action of licorice⁹.

Some analogous flavonoids, neoliquiritin (3)^{4,8}, rhamnoliquiritin (4)^{11,12}, neoisoliquiritin (7)^{4,8,10}, rhamnoisoliquiritin (8) and licuraside (9)¹¹ have been isolated by Russian workers from licorice. These known flavonoid glycosides are not contained in the FM 100-fraction.

2 liquiritin	R	R'
3 neoliquiritin	H	glucosyl
4 rhamnoliquiritin	H	H
5 liquiritigenin	H	glucorhamnosyl
		H

6 isoliquiritin	R	R'
7 neoisoliquiritin	H	glucosyl
8 rhamnoisoliquiritin	H	H
9 licuraside	H	glucorhamnosyl
10 isoliquiritigenin	H	H

Survey on the Flavonoid Compounds in Various Species of Licorice :

A comparative study by means of TLC on the methanolic extracts of various species of licorice which are available in drug market has shown characteristic patterns of flavonoid distribution, which could be used for chemotaxonomical identification of *Glycyrrhiza* species.

The species of licorice which are commonly available for medicinal use are as follows :

flavonols, isoflavones, isoflavanone, pterocarpan, coumestans, 3-arylcoumarins, isoflavones and isoflavans.

Some characters of the flavonoid compounds of each group isolated from several kinds of licorice are described below.

Chalcones

Almost all the naturally occurring chalcones so far known possess a hydroxyl at the 2'-position in

Tongpei Licorice (North-eastern Chinese licorice)	<i>Glycyrrhiza uralensis</i> Fisch. et DC
Sipei Licorice* (North-western Chinese licorice)	—
Sinkiang Licorice*	—
Persian Licoric	<i>G. glabra</i> L. var. <i>β-violacea</i> Boiss
Russian Licorice	<i>G. glabra</i> L. var. <i>grandulifera</i> Reg. et Herd.
Spanish Licorice	<i>G. glabra</i> L. var. <i>typica</i> Reg. et Herd.

The original plant species of each commercially available licorice cited above is based on some well established literatures, but some* have not been definitely identified.

A-ring, so that chalcones and flavanones are interconvertible at that position. Thus it would be reasonable to find that a chalcone, isoliquiritin (6), and its aglycone, isoliquiritigenin (10), are co-existing with the

plate: silica gel GF₂₅₄,
solvent: benzene, ether (4:1)

Fig. 1

The roots of *Glycyrrhiza echinata* L. and *G. pallidiflora* Maxim. which are not used medicinally as having less sweet taste have also been studied as references.

The flavonoid compounds isolated from licorice are classified chemically into chalcones, flavanones, flavones,

corresponding flavanone, liquiritin (2), and its aglycone, liquiritigenin (5), in various species of *Glycyrrhiza*.

Meanwhile, an unusual chalcone, echinatin (11), which possesses no hydroxyl at the 2' (or 6') position was isolated by Furuya *et al*^{1,2}. from callus tissue of

10 isoliquiritigenin [A,C,F]

11 echinatin [C,E]

12 licochalcone A [C]

13 licochalcone B [C]

Glycyrrhiza echinata, and subsequently by our group two other compounds of such type, licochalcones A (12) and B (13)¹⁴, were isolated along with echinatin (11) and isoliquiritigenin (10)¹⁵ from Sinkiang licorice. The biosynthesis of echinatin has been studied¹⁶ as described later using the callus culture of *G. echinata*, which has led a name, biogenetical retrochalcone, for this group of compounds. It has been noted that licochalcones A and B and echinatin give a distinct ion peak (m/e M-31) in their mass spectra. It is elucidated by the mass fragmentation of echinatin, as an example, to characterize the retrochalcones. (Chart 1).

Flavanones

Liquiritigenin (5) was first isolated⁴ as the aglycone of a glucoside, liquiritin (2), a major flavonoid component of licorice extracts. Liquiritigenin (5) would be distributed in various kinds of licorice in a very low content, while it has been isolated actually only from Tongpei licorice.

From Russian licorice, glabrol (16) was isolated as an optically active flavanone whose stereochemistry was established by means of the circular dichroism¹⁷. Two other known flavanones, isobavachin (14)¹⁸ and 7,4'-dihydroxy-6,8-di- γ -dimethylallylflavanone (15)¹⁹ were isolated as the constituents of *G. pallidiflora*²⁰.

Flavones and Flavonol

It is noted that flavones and flavonols were found in the especially limited kinds of licorice.

Licoflavone A (18) and a known flavone, 7,4'-dihydroxyflavone (17), were isolated from Sinkiang licorice²¹. Kumatakenin (19) which is known as a constituent of *Alpinia kumatake* (Zingiberaceae)²² was isolated in a fairly good yield from Sipei licorice as its characteristic principle²³. It exhibits an intensive golden-yellow fluorescence under UV illumination (366 nm) on a TLC plate after spraying with 10% H₂SO₄, and heating which can be used for identification of Sipei licorice. Licoflavonol (20), a kaempferol derivative having a γ -dimethylallyl group at the 6-position, was also isolated from Sipei licorice²³.

Chart 1

* The alphabetic letter in [] attached to the name of compound under the structural formula indicates the species of licorice from which the compound has been isolated:
A: Tongpei licorice; B: Sipei licorice; C: Sinkiang licorice; D: Russian licorice; E: *Glycyrrhiza echinata* root;
F: *Glycyrrhiza pallidiflora* root.

5 liquiritigenin [A]

14 isobavacnin [F]

15 unnamed [F]

16 glabrol [D]

17 7,4'-dihydroxyflavone [C]

18 licoiflavone A [C]

Isoflavones and Isoflavanones

It has been well known that isoflavonoid compounds are widely distributed in leguminous plants. Formononetin, 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-isoflavone (21), which is the most common isoflavone among them and seems to be a key intermediate of biosynthesis of this group of compounds also occurs in all the species of licorice so far examined.

19 kumatakenin [B]

20 licoiflavonol [B]

Licorice is a good source of isoflavones or isoflavonoids, and glabrone²⁴ (23), licoisoflavones A (25)²⁵ and B (26)¹⁵ were isolated from various kinds of licorice. Licoisoflavanone (27) which is corresponding to licoisoflavone B (26) was obtained as a racemate from Sinkiang licorice.¹⁵ Among the isoflavones of licorice, licoricone (24) is unique with respect of

21 formononetin [A,B,C,D,E,F]

22 afrosin [F]

23 glabrone [D]

24 licoricone [A,B]

25 licoisoflavone A [B]

26 licoisoflavone B [C]

27 licoisoflavanone [C]

possessing a phloroglucinol-type structure in B-ring.^{24,26} That is the only example of such naturally occurring flavonoids.

Pterocarpan and Coumestans

As a pterocarpan derivative, medicarpin (28) which is commonly distributed in leguminous plants was isolated from the roots of *G. echinata*²⁶ and *G. pallidiflora*.²⁰

Coumestan and 3-arylcoumarin are regarded to be isoflavonoids from biosynthetic viewpoint.²⁸ Although the first example of coumestan was found in a Compositae plant, all other coumestans so far known have been isolated from leguminous plants, while 3-aryl-coumarins occur only in the latter.²⁸ As the coumestan derivatives, glycyrol (29) and 5-O-methylglycyrol (30) were isolated from both Tongpei²⁹ and Sipei licorice,²⁸ while isoglycyrol (31) was obtained from the former²⁹ and glycyrin (32) from the latter.³⁰ These coumestans are useful for identification of various species of *Glycyrrhiza*, since they are easily identified by the strong blue (for 29, 30 and 31) or weak green (for 32) fluorescent spots on TLC under the illumination of UV-light (366 nm). When a $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyl group is located at the *ortho* position of a phenolic hydroxyl, a chroman ring closure occurs by the action of methanolic HCl as shown in the case of glycyrol (29)

converting into isoglycyrol (31). If the hydroxyl is blocked or absent at the *ortho* position of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyl group, the chroman ring is not formed, but solvent is added at the double bond of the side-chain.²⁹

Chart 2

Isoflavenes and Isoflavans

From Russian licorice, an isoflavene derivative, glabrene (34)²⁴, was isolated, which is biogenetically related to an isoflavone, glabrone (23), occurring in the same species. A new member of this group has been found in *G. pallidiflora* and named pallidiflorene (33) which has been derived³⁰ from medicarpin (28) by one step reaction with HCl. (Chart 3).

In general isoflavenes are very unstable to suggest the reason of their rare occurrence. Licoricidin (37) which was isolated from Tongpei³¹ and Sipei licorice³⁵ was the first example of naturally occurring isoflavan.

Almost the same time, the occurrence of several isoflavans in leguminous plants has been reported by two other groups independently.³² Later glabridin (36) has been isolated from Russian licorice,¹⁷ while vestitol (35) has been obtained from Tongpei licorice and the roots of *G. echinata*²⁷ and *G. pallidiflora*.²⁰ The stereochemistry of glabridin has been established by means of ORD.

Chart 3

33 pallidiflorene [F]

34 glabrene [D]

35 vestitol [A,E,F]

36 glabridin [D]

37 licoricidin [A,B]

The mass spectrometry is effectively applied for the elucidation of structures of isoflavans.

As shown in chart 4, significant ion peaks indicate the location of substituents in A and B rings of isoflavans. Thus in the case of licoricidin, the locations of one each methoxyl, hydroxyl and γ, γ -dimethylallyl groupings in the A-ring, and two hydroxyls in the B-rings were determined mass-spectrometrically.

Two hydroxyls in the B-ring of licoricidin were proved to be located at 2' and 4' positions by means of PMR-spectrum giving a singlet and an AB-type signal of aromatic protons. The locations of a methoxyl and a γ, γ -dimethylallyl grouping in the A-ring were determined also by the NOE study of the PMR spectrum of licoricidin trimethyl ether.

Chart 4

Chart 5

Biosynthesis of Retrochalcones

As mentioned before, a group of chalcones having unusual structure with no hydroxyl at the 2'-position were found in the roots of some species of *Glycyrrhiza*, and named biogenetical retrochalcone.

In literatures there are another examples of such type of naturally occurring chalcones: Two unnamed chalcones (2,4-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-chalcone and 2,4-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-5-methyl-chalcone) isolated from dragon blood resin (*Calmus drago* (Palmae))³³ hyssopigenin (2,4,6-trihydroxy-3',4'-methylenedioxychalcone) from *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (Curciferace)³⁴.

A biosynthetic study has been carried out using callus tissues of *G. echinata*¹⁶.

In considering the co-occurrence of normal flavonoid with retrochalcones in Sinkiang licorice and the root and callus tissue of *G. echinata*, a normal chalcone, isoliquiritigenin, has been taken as the precursor of retrochalcone.

[3,5-T] Isoliquiritigenin was fed to the callus tissue of *G. echinata* which was cultured under shaking for 2 days in the dark at 26°C in White's medium containing 2,4-D (0.1 ppm) and yeast extracts (0.1%). On degradation of echinatin isolated from the callus tissue, the incorporation of tritium was found in the A-ring (85.5%). [3-¹⁴C] Cinnamic acid and [1-¹⁴C] cinnamic acid were also fed to the culture of callus tissue of *G. echinata* and treated as above to prove the location

of ¹⁴C in the carbonyl of *p*-hydroxy acetophenone, and the aldehyde of 2-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, respectively.

Thus the following scheme involving a conversion of carbonyl of chalcone has been proposed for the biosynthesis of echinatin, and this scheme would be adopted to other members of retrochalcones.

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